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2 **The Evolution of Display Technologies for Antibody Drug Discovery**

3
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21 **Keywords:** Antibody engineering, antibody discovery, bispecific antibody, CAR-T, computational
22 design, directed evolution, display technology, high-throughput screening

24 **Abstract**

25 Display technologies are a class of experimental methods that enable a direct association
26 between protein function and DNA sequence. Since the original introduction of phage display in
27 1985, antibody display technologies have undergone many successful iterations that amplified
28 capabilities for drug discovery. Recent advances build on these foundations to accommodate new
29 antibody modalities, improve library size, accelerate functional discovery, and make the most of
30 experimental data by leveraging computational analysis and structure prediction. Here we discuss
31 how recent advances in protein display are being applied to solve a broad range of problems in
32 antibody drug discovery, immunology, and biotechnology.

33 **Highlights:**

- 34 • Display technologies, including phage, yeast, mRNA/ribosome, and mammalian display, have
35 played a pivotal role in antibody discovery and engineering, leading to the discovery of life-
36 saving therapies.
- 37 • Since their inception, these foundational technologies have sprouted new approaches for
38 antibody discovery. Here, we cover recent advancements, which include library generation (*in*
39 *vivo* and *in cellulose*), engineered antibody formats, conditional binders, function-first screening,
40 library vs. library screening, and drug safety screening.
- 41 • We discuss the influence of display technologies on the development of machine learning,
42 artificial intelligence, and rational protein design for antibody discovery & engineering.
- 43 • While display technologies were originally developed for antibody panning based on affinity,
44 they have been crucial for the development of novel tools that can drive new growth in
45 antibody therapeutics for many years to come.

46 **Outstanding questions:**

- 47 • How have antibody display technologies expanded into new areas in recent years?
- 48 • What are the major challenges facing current technologies in high-throughput antibody
- 49 display and selection?
- 50 • What are the most effective ways to discover CAR-T molecules?
- 51 • How can screening studies be effectively performed to capture functional information?
- 52 • How can novel library generation methods be used to increase screening capacity?
- 53 • How can advances in library vs. library display be used to provide comprehensive data on
- 54 protein-protein interactions?
- 55 • How can advances in rational protein design be used to accelerate antibody discovery
- 56 efforts?
- 57 • How can new experimental display methods be used together with computational
- 58 approaches?

59 Introduction

60 **Display technologies** (see Glossary) have continually supported fundamental studies of
61 immune proteins along with translational drug discovery over the past five decades. A display
62 technology physically links a protein variant **library** to its nucleic acid sequences. Using protein
63 display, researchers can selectively **pan** protein libraries based on functional criteria (most
64 commonly antigen **affinity**) and simultaneously isolate their selected DNA/RNA sequences.
65 Display technologies thus enable high-throughput selection for *protein function*, using *nucleic acid*
66 libraries as both a source template and the refined product. As it is much simpler to analyze and
67 amplify complex libraries of nucleic acids than protein molecules, this unique physical linkage of
68 protein genotype and phenotype has made display technologies one of the most powerful,
69 sensitive, flexible, and widely used techniques in protein engineering.

70 Reported fifty years ago in 1975, Köhler and Milstein achieved the very first production of
71 **monoclonal antibodies (mAb)** using **hybridomas** generated from immunized mice, leading
72 directly to the first monoclonal antibodies for clinical use. Hybridomas represented an early way
73 to connect antibody function with DNA sequence. Though hybridomas were the dominant
74 antibody discovery technology for many years, they have several limitations including that each
75 hybridoma must be individually tested in well plates, the antibodies are sometimes poorly
76 produced, the hybridomas can be genetically unstable with limited replicative potential, and
77 redosing of mouse-derived antibodies is limited by **human anti-mouse antibody (HAMA)**
78 responses. Advanced **humanization** technologies and mice expressing human antibody genes
79 can now alleviate HAMA formation. Still, the throughput limitations of hybridomas inspired a
80 decades-long search for new approaches.

81 A seminal leap forward came a decade later with the invention of phage display by George
82 Smith and colleagues in 1985. In phage display, a desired polypeptide is usually expressed as a
83 fusion with filamentous phage coat protein gene product III (pIII). Phage particles physically
84 contain both the nucleic acid genotype (as genomic DNA) and the phenotype (the displayed fusion

85 protein). This landmark technology enabled protein affinity selection on a massive scale. At the
86 beginning of the 1990's, Gregory Winter and colleagues displayed antibodies on phage in both
87 **scFv** and **Fab** formats, thus recapitulating antibody specificities on the surface of phage particles.
88 These early advances revolutionized therapeutic antibody development and inspired several
89 generations of subsequent display technologies, including yeast display, mammalian display, and
90 ribosomal display (**Figure 1**). Other important advances have included **function-first screening**,
91 precision library construction, analysis via **next-generation DNA sequencing**, and computational
92 data mining. Here we outline the most recent advances in antibody display technologies, along
93 with brief descriptions of the historical contexts in which they were created.

94

95 **Early Branches - The Established Display Technologies**

96 Several display technologies were introduced following phage display, each based on
97 affinity selection and with unique strengths and limitations (**Figure 1**). Most display platforms
98 follow a workflow akin to: 1) a diverse library of protein variants is generated, 2) a library of
99 proteins is displayed on cells or particles, linking protein (phenotype) to RNA/DNA (genotype), 3)
100 affinity panning physically separates binders from non-binders, 4) nucleic acids encoding the
101 enriched binders are amplified, and 5) the cycle repeats at Step 2 to further refine the binding
102 pool. Sometimes, additional diversity is introduced when the cycle is repeated, enabling directed
103 evolution over subsequent rounds. Key differences across the established display technologies
104 include supported library sizes, mechanisms for diversity generation, displayed protein copy
105 number (and therefore **avidity**), ease/simplicity/speed of library construction, displayable
106 proteins, cellular expression machinery for post-translational modifications, and supported
107 selection techniques (**Table 1**).

108

109 **Display Innovations for Engineered Antibody Modalities**

110 Bispecific and other multispecific antibodies are synthetic antibodies that contain two (or
111 more, in the case of multispecific antibodies) binding arms [1]. **Bispecific antibodies (bsAbs)**
112 can be categorized into two groups based on their mechanism of action: **combinatorial** or
113 **obligate** [2]. Combinatorial bsAb activity can be approximately achieved with a mixture of the two
114 parental mAbs. The advantages of manufacturing and administering a single bsAb product, rather
115 than two distinct mAbs, can make combinatorial bsAbs attractive for many applications. In
116 contrast, obligate bsAbs have effects that are not simply the summation of the two parental
117 antibodies, enabling biological activity that cannot be recapitulated by simply combining the two
118 separate monoclonal antibodies in a mixture [2]. Bispecific T cell engagers (BiTEs) are among
119 the most extensively researched obligate bsAbs, and have led to therapies for the treatment of
120 hematological malignancies [3,4] and solid tumors [5,6]. BiTEs are composed of one arm that
121 binds to a **tumor-associated antigen (TAA)** and another arm that binds CD3, recruiting T cells
122 to form an **immunological synapse** with tumor cells while providing T cell activation signals
123 through the CD3 machinery. Other obligate bsAbs bind transferrin on one arm to enable cellular
124 transcytosis through the blood-brain-barrier, where the second arm of the antibody can elicit its
125 therapeutic effects [9]. Bispecific antibodies can also recruit protein heterodimers and modulate
126 their activity (eg., HER2/HER3, FGFR/Klotho, etc.).

127 bsAbs come in a range of configurations that are dependent on desired application and
128 biophysical requirements [10]. There are over 100 bsAbs formats in research and/or clinical use,
129 and currently the field is moving into tri-specifics and beyond [2]. bsAbs can be further divided
130 into fragment-based bsAbs, which include only the antigen-binding regions, versus bsAbs that
131 contain a fragment crystallizable (Fc) region. Fragment-based bsAbs have simplified production
132 but lower persistence *in vivo* due to their inability to recycle via the neonatal Fc receptor (FcRN).
133 bsAbs with an Fc region are thus appealing for their extended half-life and native-like formats, but
134 they can suffer from chain association issues where the mispairing of light chains and/or the

135 association of two of the same heavy chains decreases production yield of the desired construct
136 [2].

137 Achieving correct chain pairing is a prerequisite for screening bispecifics using display
138 technologies. An early method to address heavy chain association issues was the knobs-into-
139 holes technology, where separate mutations on each of the heavy chains (C_H3) enabled selective
140 assembly of two distinct heavy chains in a bispecific manner [11]. Achieving proper chain
141 association of light chains has been more difficult because light chains interact with heavy chains
142 at two interfaces: once between the variable regions of heavy (V_H) and light (V_L) chains, and
143 again between the constant regions of heavy (C_H1) and light (C_L) chains [12]. One approach to
144 circumvent light chain association issues uses a common light chain, i.e., the same light chain
145 that would be used in both binding arms [2]. Other strategies include controlled Fab-arm exchange
146 (cFAE) — where each mAb is produced in separate cells, the heavy-chain interactions are broken,
147 and the respective half-IgGs are reassembled into a bispecific antibody [13] — and domain
148 crossover, which involves swapping the light chain and V_H – C_H1 domain on one binding arm [14].
149 Recent technologies use amino acid substitutions in C_H1 and C_L to promote preferential
150 interactions via disulfide bond engineering [15] or electrostatic steering [16], ultimately decreasing
151 mispairing. Mispairing in bsAbs has been addressed with Rosetta based on favorable hydrogen
152 bonding between the heavy and light chains [12]. These recent technologies are advantageous
153 for display studies because they enable bsAb production from a single cell, which is less
154 manufacturing-intensive than other methods like cFAE [16].

155 The biological function of multi-specific antibodies depends on a complex interplay of
156 geometry, binding affinities of each arm, and agonistic and antagonistic activities. Display
157 technologies are commonly used to generate or preserve appropriate bsAb drug activity after
158 generating large numbers of potential candidates during early discovery, especially for affinity
159 tuning and precision cell selectivity [17]. As multi-specifics continue to evolve in geometry, valency,

160 and format, new display approaches must be devised to recapitulate these formats and establish
161 functional assays that accurately assess bispecific activity at scale.

162

163 **Chimeric Antigen Receptor Immunotherapies**

164 **Chimeric antigen receptors (CARs)** are another innovation platform accelerated by
165 display technologies. Conventional CAR T cells fuse an antibody binding domain (often scFv,
166 **single-chain heavy chain domain (VHH)**, or other protein binding domain) to a hinge domain
167 (CD8 or CD28), a transmembrane domain (CD8 or CD28), and an intracellular costimulatory
168 domain (CD28 or 4-1-BB, followed by CD3 ζ). These constructs enable an engineered T cell to
169 recognize and kill target cells; CAR variants have also been introduced for other immune cell
170 types including NK cells, macrophages and Tregs.

171 The first clinically approved CARs recognize proteins specific to an entire cell lineage,
172 enabling cures where on-target off-tumor toxicity are clinically manageable (e.g., CD19 expressed
173 on all B cells). A common approach clones enriched scFv after phage panning into CAR T vectors
174 for functional activity screening, thereby combining high-throughput affinity selection in phage with
175 activity selection in mammalian cells. For example, an early study converted a phage library to a
176 CAR T library and showed that functional binders expressed in Jurkat cells can be sorted by FACs
177 for the T cell activation marker CD69 [18]. Additional fluorescent reporters of T cell activation have
178 been reported for CAR T screening, including nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B) and nuclear factor of
179 activated T cells (NFAT) [19] or the cytokine IL-2 [20]. These efforts enabled the sorting of CARs
180 with both binding and potential for on-target activation against ROR1 and NYESO1-A2:01 MHCs
181 respectively.

182 In addition to the CAR binding domains, CAR T display has also been used to optimize the
183 transmembrane and intracellular signaling domains. One study screened a library of binders with
184 different signaling domain combinations (CD28-CD3 ζ , 4-1-BBz-CD3 ζ , or CD3 ζ) [21]. An
185 expanded screen explored a combinatorial library of 40 costimulatory and coinhibitory receptor

186 intracellular signaling domains, transduced in T cells, where a BAF-R costimulatory domain
187 showed improved persistence and equal cytotoxicity compared to the conventional CD28 and 4-
188 1-BBz costimulatory domains [22]. CAR display in mammalian cell lines thus provides a functional
189 means to evaluate CARs in their native, drug-like context.

190 The next generation in CAR T cell therapy seeks to expand the landscape of actionable
191 targets like TAAs, as very few truly tumor-specific antigens exist that are not expressed in healthy
192 tissues. One solution to expanding tumor-specific targets is by targeting tumor drivers presented
193 on MHC. While this strategy significantly expands the number of tumor targets, it creates unique
194 protein engineering challenges in targeting the 4-5 residues of the peptide that is exposed from
195 the MHC cleft while avoiding cross-reactivities with biophysically similar **pMHC**. Using a pMHC
196 targeting strategy, we recently exploited the aberrant but consistent expression of intracellular
197 PHOX2B that is normally expressed in fetal development, to target pediatric neuroblastoma [23].
198 We identified scFvs binding to PHOX2B-MHCs by Retained Display (ReD), a phage display
199 method where scFv-phage are retained within the cytoplasm of *E. coli* expressing target protein,
200 enabling sorting for on-target binders through cellular staining and flow cytometry – substantially
201 expanding the throughput of on- and off-target binding as compared to conventional ELISA-based
202 screens. This peptide-centric CAR demonstrates highly selective tumor killing through PHOX2B
203 and has recently entered a Phase I clinical trial (NCT07007117). Recently, NeoCARs (KRAS
204 mutant targeting CAR) have been developed to target a single point mutation in KRAS G12V
205 pMHC using the same ReD method [24]. Overall, integrating display libraries with functional CAR
206 screening represents a powerful trend in protein drug discovery. As the number of pMHC targets
207 expands [24], new display technologies will evolve to deliver high-affinity, high-selectivity binding
208 for this difficult class of targets.

209 Display technologies are well-suited to optimize CAR T against TAAs, and screening can
210 identify CARs with the appropriate sensitivity window between on-target efficacy vs. on-target off-
211 tumor toxicity. To further improve the sensitivity window for TAAs, logic-gating strategies where

212 the presence of two TAAs (AND-gate) or presence of one TAA and not the presence of a healthy
213 tissue membrane protein (NOT-gate) can be used in context with functional library screening.
214 These and other logic gating strategies to improve targeted cell recognition of CARs are reviewed
215 in [25] and [26].

216

217 **Function-First Screening of Soluble Drugs**

218 A major shift is underway to use display screening campaigns to analyze additional
219 functional activities beyond antigen binding affinity. Traditional screening methods effectively
220 produce binders, but are often laborious, inefficient, and in many cases not productive for drug
221 discovery that requires relatively rare functional activity like receptor agonism, antagonism, or
222 virus neutralization. For obligate bsAbs and receptor agonists, higher affinity can be anti-
223 correlated with functional activity and/or favorable pharmacodynamics [27,28]. Tethered
224 mammalian or yeast cell display have been coupled with functional readouts related to antagonist
225 or agonist activity [29–31]. Several groups have used microfluidic devices or small compartments
226 to analyze secreted proteins by capturing two cells together, where one cell reports functional
227 drug activity (phenotype) and the other cell encodes and secretes the antibody (genotype); the
228 droplet or compartment provides the physical association [32,33]. As one example, Nishimoto et
229 al. used hollow hydrogel microparticles to encapsulate reporter T cells along with hybridomas to
230 identify anti-CD3 T cell activators [34]. Other efforts leveraged oil emulsions to encapsulate cells
231 of interest to screen for antibodies with autocrine binding activity [35], receptor agonist activity
232 [36], activating BiTEs [36,37], and virus neutralization [38]. One issue with dual-cell approaches
233 is that they often require advanced technologies to sort droplets (known as fluorescence-activated
234 droplet sorting, or FADS), incorporating complex microfluidics along with fluorescence and sort
235 capabilities. Throughput is further limited by the probability of combining one secreter cell and
236 one reporter cell together in the same droplet. To address these challenges, our group combined
237 reporter and secretion mechanisms into the same cell line for an efficient functional activity screen

238 [39]. This approach obviates the need for FADS and enables high-throughput screening of
239 antibodies in their final drug-like form using a standard flow cytometer.

240

241 **Conditional Binders**

242 Many antibodies have dose-limiting toxicities that narrow their **therapeutic index**. Recent
243 studies have exploited unique tissue features (e.g., of the tumor microenvironment, TME) to
244 achieve local antibody activity [40]. For example, the known overexpression of proteases in the
245 TME inspired the use of pro-antibodies with **paratope** masks that release after a protease digest
246 [40]. This approach has been applied to a range of antibody therapies, including **immune**
247 **checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs)** and BiTEs [40–43]. Display technologies have been employed to
248 generate the protease-cleavable linkers used in these masks, an example of non-antibody
249 display. Another strategy exploits the Warburg effect, where tumor cells preferentially use
250 glycolysis and produce lactic acid that reduces the pH of the TME [44]. Low pH-binding antibodies
251 use the lower pKa of histidine to broaden the therapeutic index of ICIs and TAA-targeting
252 immunotherapies, and are often discovered using phage display or rational protein design [44–
253 46]. ATP is elevated in the TME up to three orders of magnitude [47]. To exploit ATP concentration
254 differences, **synthetic libraries** have been screened for antibodies that bind cooperatively to ATP
255 and a target TAA, which decreases antigen binding to healthy tissue outside of the TME [48–50].
256 A significant advantage of ATP- and pH-dependent antibodies is that their activated state is
257 reversible, unlike pro-antibodies, which remain active after proteolysis of the peptide mask.
258 Together, new screening methods built upon display libraries are enabling conditional specificity
259 and the development of TME-specific drug products.

260

261 **Safety Screening and Risk Reduction**

262 Eliminating off-target binding is critical for clinical therapies, as **cross-reactive antibodies**
263 have poor *in vivo* persistence and can lead to drug toxicity. Polyspecific (or **polyreactive**)

264 antibodies are classically detected using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) to defined
265 antigens or with HEp-2 assays in well plates, sometimes with additional affinity measurements
266 [51]. Capitalizing on display technologies, recent efforts used DNA **barcoded libraries** in cell-free
267 systems [52] and yeast display [53,54] to survey antibody binding across the human proteome.
268 pMHC-specific binders in CAR-T or TCR-T cells present distinct challenges, as cross-reactivity
269 can lead to fatal off-target toxicity [55]. To screen for pMHC reactivity, single-chain pMHC libraries
270 have also been displayed on yeast [56] and on mammalian cells [57,58]. While algorithms like
271 sCRAP can be used to predict biosimilar peptides within the human genome [23], high-throughput
272 display technologies offer a means to experimentally assess off-target reactivity across a broad
273 biochemical landscape.

274

275 **Continuous Library Generation and *in cellulo* Techniques**

276 The library size of many display technologies is limited by electroporation; both phage
277 display and yeast display are practically restricted to 10^9 - 10^{11} variants. Mammalian display is
278 further limited by the transduction efficiency of cells, the **multiplicity of infection (MOI)** when
279 using lentivirus, and by cell culture density, with upper limits of around 10^6 - 10^8 clones. To efficiently
280 expand library diversity and enable **directed evolution**, several methods have been introduced
281 that achieve continuous library generation paired to selection. In general, the major challenge is
282 to generate diversity in a desired target protein, without disruptions to the background genome
283 that lead to non-viability of encoding cells. One continuous mutagenesis system, Automomous
284 Hypermutation Yeast Surface Display (AHEAD), combines an orthogonal error-prone polymerase
285 along with yeast surface display to rapidly evolve high affinity VHHs [59]. Others have used a
286 fusion protein between error-prone polymerases and a CRISPR-nickase to perform mutagenesis
287 inside cells, enabling function-based continuous directed evolution [60,61]. Recently, Cazier et al.
288 expressed RAG1 and RAG2 proteins involved in VDJ recombination in yeast, recombining the
289 VH-CDR3 of known scFvs in ~ 1% of cells after four days [62].

290 An increasingly common approach is also using the native mouse B cell diversity
291 generation machinery to generate libraries for antibody optimization. In these systems, targeted
292 genomic integration inserts a template antibody into fertilized oocytes [63–66]. The entire mouse
293 immune response thus becomes an engineered display library diversified from the template gene.
294 Most efforts with these technologies have focused on infectious disease applications, including
295 HIV-1 and malaria, which are especially challenging for clinical antibody discovery due to the need
296 for exceptional antibody protective potency and breadth. As *in cellulo* technologies continue to
297 mature, they have the potential to open avenues to new function-based continuous evolution
298 methods.

299

300 **Library vs. Library Screening**

301 **Library vs. library** discovery platforms encode two separate libraries – often one for
302 antigens and another for antibodies – for comprehensive characterization of target/antigen pairs
303 [67]. Several platforms with varying configurations have been reported for library vs. library
304 display. One recent study used yeast display to express two proteins of interest connected by a
305 protease-cleavable linker, efficiently detecting interacting proteins after a proteolytic cleavage step
306 [68]. Because each clone is expressed on the surface of a single yeast cell, this approach is
307 remarkably high throughput compared to most available library vs. library technologies. Another
308 approach combined ribosome scFv display with mammalian cell antigen expression to map
309 antibody:antigen interaction landscapes using Drop-Seq [69]. Other efforts used engineered
310 lentivirus displaying a protein – an antibody, an antigen, or pMHC – to infect a cell library in a
311 protein interaction-specific manner and read out the antibody:antigen pair [70,71]. Yeast systems
312 where yeast mating is enhanced by antibody:antigen interactions have also been reported [72,73].

313 A limitation for some library vs. library technologies is the inability to display complex
314 proteins on at least one of the two libraries, including potential differences in post-translational
315 modifications that hinder identification of certain interacting proteins, and the difficulties in de-

316 coupling individual interactions within complex mixtures. Library vs. library technologies are also
317 subject to heightened screening noise and bias compared to single library screening technologies
318 (polyreactive binders can be particularly problematic), but with careful experimental controls these
319 concerns can be addressed. Next-generation sequencing (NGS) provides a major advance for
320 library:library technologies in dissecting the full scope of protein:protein interactions, while also
321 helping to identify the potential noise and bias associated with these platforms. The recent
322 proliferation of library vs. library approaches promises rapid progress to improve knowledge and
323 accelerate drug discovery with these technologies in the coming years. As techniques evolve to
324 de-couple individual binding specificities from library:library screens, new capabilities will emerge
325 to survey complex protein/protein interaction networks, assess cross-reactivities at scale, and
326 generate rich datasets that train machine learning algorithms for improved computational
327 predictions.

328

329 **NGS-Enabled Machine Learning to Optimize Binders**

330 The introduction of NGS has transformed display technologies and antibody discovery.
331 Prior to NGS, complete characterization of library diversity was technically prohibitive, and a
332 limited number of clones were selected for sequencing and characterization after screening
333 rounds. After its introduction, NGS was rapidly adopted in antibody discovery, and has now been
334 used with every display platform, enabling library-scale analyses and prioritization of clones based
335 on quantitative representation, homology, and other properties (**Box 1**). Large datasets generated
336 using NGS have naturally led to machine learning data mining to analyze underlying
337 characteristics of binders. Machine learning requires large data, and library enrichment against a
338 target protein (**positive selection**) versus an off-target protein (**negative selection**) is often
339 useful for model training [74–79]. As one of many examples, a deep learning model trained on
340 NGS data collected from two rounds of affinity selections against anti-kynurenine (metabolite)
341 enabled the generation of binders against kynurenine with 1,800-fold better dissociation constants

342 [80]. Machine learning can also be used to rescue failed selections. Kawada et al. used
343 enrichment data from a failed selection against galactin-3 and produced a machine-learning
344 guided variant library, then screened the library to identify low micromolar VHHs with affinity for
345 galactin-3 [81].

346 Machine learning models have also been effectively used to identify antibodies with
347 advantages or disadvantages in developability metrics, such as polyreactivity or a propensity to
348 aggregate at high concentrations [82]. These predictive computational models complement
349 display libraries and selection-based readouts, adding an additional selective filter for molecules
350 with a high likelihood for successful downstream development. The convergence of large-scale
351 data collection enabled by low-cost NGS along with advances in computational technologies will
352 drive a new era of computationally-informed protein optimization.

353

354 ***In silico* immunotherapy design**

355 A new era of “*in silico* panning” is emerging, enabling synergies between rational design,
356 directed evolution, and computational data mining. In brief, deep learning models trained on
357 evolutionary data encoded by multiple sequence alignments (MSAs) and pairwise residues
358 capturing geometric and biochemical characteristics from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) have
359 given rise to accurate protein prediction models, including AlphaFold [83,84], Rosetta Fold [85],
360 and ESMFold [86] (reviewed in [87]). Learned protein information from protein structure prediction
361 models have been combined with diffusion models (RFDiffusion [88]) and inverse folding
362 algorithms (ProteinMPNN [89] and ESM-IF [90]) to generate *de novo* binders to protein targets
363 with improved on-target binding rates. Integrated models have been developed from these
364 concepts (BindCraft [91], CHAI-1 [92], CHAI-2 [93], Boltz-1 [94], Boltz-2 [95]), which report
365 enhanced success rates for high-affinity binders against various targets.

366 These methods have been mostly successful in generating binders with rigid structures
367 (typically helical bundles). However, *de novo* antibody design presents a difficult challenge due to

368 limited antibody-antigen structural data and high conformational variation in CDR loops, especially
369 the non-templated variable-length CDR3s. Antibody-specific structure prediction methods like
370 IgFold [96] can more accurately recapitulate CDR3 loops compared to generalist models like
371 AlphaFold2. Integrated structural antibody design pipelines like ABodyBuilder2 [97] are optimized
372 to generate antibodies and VHs. One *in silico* antibody discovery pipeline used RFDiffusion to
373 generate VHs against a panel of target antigens [98]. Screening of designed proteins was
374 performed by yeast display (8,000 constructs) or bacterial display (95 constructs), and nanomolar
375 affinity VHs were identified. A recent workflow from Genentech called Lab-in-the-loop [99] (LitL)
376 integrated computational and physical screening pipelines. LitL begins with multiple methods
377 (PropEN, LaMBO, dWJS, DyAb, SeqVDM) to diversify a starting antibody first identified by
378 conventional panning. Each design is annotated with predicted properties encompassing
379 expression, binding affinity, and non-specificity from internally trained models, and antibodies with
380 potential off-target reactivities or post-translational modifications are removed. Authors report
381 affinity improvement of 3- to 100-fold within 4 iterations, while eliminating developability risks. The
382 incorporation of *in silico* methods to improve developability and function of immunotherapies are
383 powerful tools for new drug development.

384 While remarkable progress has been achieved in the past several years, *de novo* methods
385 are still in their infancy and uncertainty remains as to functional potency, developability,
386 immunogenicity and pharmacodynamics compared to well-characterized antibody discovery
387 platforms. Rapid advancements in computational techniques and the ability to scale these
388 methods based on computational power will drive rapid and iterative evolution of computational
389 design methods, with the potential to radically alter therapeutic discovery.

390

391 In past decades, the remarkable technological breakthroughs in antibody display occurred
392 mostly through experimental advances, enabling new classes of therapeutics that contributed
393 fantastic improvements in human health. Display platforms have since continued to evolve and

394 are now becoming closely integrated with machine learning data analysis and computational
395 molecular design. As we enter an exciting era of new technologies for therapeutic development
396 and their clinical applications, we are reminded of the incredible advantages of linking genotype
397 with phenotype at scale.

398 **Acknowledgements**

399 We thank all the leaders, instructors, lecturers, and students of the long-running Antibody
400 Engineering & Display Technologies course, held annually at Cold Spring Harbor
401 Laboratories, for fostering a collaborative and creative environment that has shaped the
402 field and helps train the next generation of innovators. Many thanks to Camila Franca for
403 assistance with figure preparation, and Amanuella Mengiste for helpful comments. This
404 work was supported by the NIH Director's New Innovator Award (1DP2CA301080 to
405 M.Y.). M.Y. is the Bakewell Foundation-Rachleff Innovator of the Damon Runyon Cancer
406 Research Foundation (DRR-86-25) and a recipient of the Pershing Square Sohn Cancer
407 Prize. This work was delivered as part of the MATCHMAKERS and NextGen teams,
408 supported by the Cancer Grand Challenges partnership financed by CRUK (CGCATF-
409 2021/100038 to M.Y and CGCATF-2023/100009 to B.D), the National Cancer Institute
410 (CA290738-01 to M.Y and OT2CA297514 to B.D.), and The Mark Foundation for Cancer
411 Research. This work was also supported by NIH grants 1R01AI181684, 1R01AI192975,
412 1U01AI169587, and R21AI178021, and by The Mark and Lisa Schwartz AI/ML Initiative,
413 The American Cancer Society, The Gates Foundation, the Koch Institute for Cancer
414 Research, the MIT Research Support Committee, the MIT Department of Chemical
415 Engineering, and The Ragon Institute.

416

417

418 **Declaration of Interests**

419 M.Y. is the co-founder of Hula Therapeutics and the inventor on patents related to immune
420 receptors, CAR T technologies and display technologies assigned to the Children's

421 Hospital of Philadelphia and NYU Langone Health. B.J.D. is a co-inventor of patents
422 related to immune receptors and display technologies currently assigned to The
423 University of Texas at Austin, The National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases,
424 The University of Kansas, Massachusetts General Hospital, and Massachusetts Institute
425 of Technology.

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645

646 **Figure 1.** The evolution of display technologies for antibody discovery.

Box 1 – NGS as a Catalyst for Antibody Display Technologies

Next-generation sequencing (NGS) enables rapid, comprehensive analysis of gene libraries at every stage of screening. Key applications include:

Hybridoma Screening:

- Primer-barcoded well indexing allows rapid sequencing of hybridoma clones directly from screening plates.

Phage, Ribosome, Yeast, and Mammalian Display:

- Deep characterization of initial library composition.
- Identify sequences that successfully display on the desired platform.
- Track individual clones and clonal enrichment ratios across selection rounds.
- Detect rare, high-performance clones that never reach high prevalence.
- Control for replication bias between rounds.
- Generate large datasets for statistical analysis and AI/ML-driven discovery.

***In vivo* Library Generation:**

- Measure genetic diversity achieved *in vivo*.
- Follow clonal evolution throughout *in vivo* selection.

Conditional Binder Selection:

- Identify positive and negative binding variants under defined selection conditions to guide molecular engineering.

Library vs. Library Screening:

- Map comprehensive paired antibody-antigen interactions across large libraries.
- Follow polyreactive clones and determine interaction biases

Function-First Screening:

- Identify both functional and non-functional clones at every screening stage.

Drug Safety Screening:

- Efficiently assess antibody cross-reactivity on a large scale across diverse antigen panels.

Continuous Evolution:

- Detect ongoing sequence diversification along with affinity changes
- Monitor mutational hotspots and biases.

AI-Driven Antibody Discovery:

- Determine positive and negative interaction profiles under specific screening conditions.
- Assemble datasets of sufficient size and diversity to train robust AI/ML models.

647

648 **Box 1.** NGS as a catalyst for antibody display technologies.

649 **Table 1.** Brief description of established display technologies.

Display Platform	Library Size (Slavny et. al [100])	Anchor (most common)	Panning Method Description	Post-translational modifications
Phage Display	10^{10} - 10^{12}	pIII	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Phage library is added to immobilized antigen and non-specific phage are washed away. 2. Binding phage are eluted and re-amplified in <i>E. coli</i> for successive rounds of panning. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection stringency can be increased by reducing the amount of immobilized antigen. 3. Enriched binders are identified via colony picking or NGS. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-eukaryote PTMs
Yeast Display	10^8 - 10^9	Aga1p-Aga2p	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Antigen-fluorophore or antigen-magnetic bead conjugates are added to a yeast library; unbound antigen is washed away. 2. Cells are sorted using fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) or magnetic-activated cell sorting (MACS). 3. Cells are grown in culture for successive rounds of panning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection stringency can be modulated by altering gating in FACS 4. Enriched binders are identified via NGS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Native-like folding • Hypermannosylated proteins • Glycosylation differences between yeast and human cells can limit display of the human proteome, and for antigens in library vs. library screening.
Mammalian Display	10^5 - 10^8	PDGFR	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Antigen-fluorophore or antigen-magnetic bead conjugates are added to a cell library; unbound antigen is washed away. 2. Cells are sorted using fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) or magnetic-activated cell sorting (MACS). 3. Cells are grown in culture for successive rounds of panning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection stringency can be modulated by altering gating in FACS 4. Enriched binders are identified via NGS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human-like, final therapeutic form. • Especially useful for antigen libraries and in library vs. library screening
mRNA/Ribosome Display	10^{12} - 10^{15}	Stalled translation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. mRNA-protein complexes are incubated with immobilized antigen; non-specific binders are washed away 2. Bound complexes are eluted, and RT-PCR is performed amplify cDNA from binders. 3. Additional panning rounds are performed by re-transcribing DNA. 4. Enriched binders are identified via NGS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A, cell-free system

650

651 **Glossary**

- 652 1. **Antibody affinity**: strength of an antibody-target interaction.
- 653 2. **Antibody library**: a collection of antibody variants.
- 654 3. **Avidity**: cumulative strength of multivalent antibody-target interactions.
- 655 4. **Barcoded libraries**: protein libraries tagged with unique nucleic acid sequences for
656 sequencing-based identification.
- 657 5. **Bispecific antibody (bsAb)**: an engineered antibody with two distinct binding
658 arms.
- 659 6. **Chimeric antigen receptor (CAR)**: an engineered receptor that activates immune
660 cells upon antigen recognition.
- 661 7. **Combinatorial bsAbs**: bsAbs whose function can be achieved by mixing the two
662 parental antibodies.
- 663 8. **Cross-reactive antibody**: an antibody binding more than one antigen.
- 664 9. **Directed evolution**: a process of inducing mutations to gene sequences and
665 selecting for a desired phenotype.
- 666 10. **Display technology**: technologies that link nucleic acid sequence (genotype) with
667 the encoded protein (phenotype).
- 668 11. **Fragment antigen-binding region (Fab)**: a heterodimer that contains only V_H - C_H1
669 and light chain.
- 670 12. **Function-first screening**: identifying antibodies based on functional activity.
- 671 13. **HAMA**: Human anti-mouse antibodies; an immune response against murine-
672 derived immunotherapies.
- 673 14. **Humanization**: modifying an antibody sequence to increase human similarity.

- 674 **15. Hybridomas:** fused B cells and myeloma cells to support continuous growth with
675 monoclonal antibody secretion.
- 676 **16. Immune checkpoint inhibitor (ICI):** drugs blocking immune checkpoint pathways
677 to enhance immune response.
- 678 **17. Immunological synapse:** a specialized interface organizing T cell receptor–pMHC
679 interactions and costimulatory complexes for specific immune activation.
- 680 **18. Library panning:** in reference to gold panning, the isolation of proteins with specific
681 properties (binding, function) from a library of displayed proteins.
- 682 **19. Library vs. library screening:** screening antibody libraries against antigen
683 libraries.
- 684 **20. mAb:** monoclonal antibody.
- 685 **21. Multiplicity of Infection (MOI):** a ratio of infectious particles per cell during *in vitro*
686 infection.
- 687 **22. Nanobody (VHH):** camelid heavy chain only antibodies.
- 688 **23. Negative selection:** removing antibody clones with undesired activity (e.g.,
689 polyreactivity).
- 690 **24. Next generation sequencing (NGS):** a technology capable of sequencing
691 thousands of DNA fragments simultaneously.
- 692 **25. Obligate bsAbs:** bsAbs whose mechanism of action cannot be achieved by
693 combining parental mAbs.
- 694 **26. Paratope:** the antigen-binding region of an antibody.
- 695 **27. pMHC:** peptide-major histocompatibility complex recognized by T cell receptors *in*
696 *vivo*.

- 697 **28. Polyreactivity:** non-specific antibody binding.
- 698 **29. Positive selection:** selection of antibodies with desired properties.
- 699 **30. Single-chain variable fragment (scFv):** polypeptide format with antibody variable-
700 heavy and -light domains connected by a flexible linker.
- 701 **31. Synthetic library:** *in vitro* generated gene libraries.
- 702 **32. Therapeutic index:** the ratio of toxic to effective doses (TD₅₀/EC₅₀).
- 703 **33. Tumor-associated antigen (TAA):** antigen highly expressed in cancer cells relative
704 to healthy tissue.